

**IMPACTS OF PRACTICING COHABITATION AMONG THE
NIGERIAN TERTIARY INSTITUTION STUDENTS ON
ACADEMIC PERFORMANCE IN IGALALAND: A
RELIGIOUS PERSPECTIVE**

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Abstract

Cohabitation from a religious perspective is simply the act of a man and woman living together as husband and wife for emotional and sexual intimacy without being married formally. Since this act is against the religious norms and traditional values of the Igala society, anyone found in this act is seen to be committing abomination and as such, students that live together do not allow their parents and relations to know. This study examines the challenge of the practice of cohabitation among the tertiary institutions' students on academic performance in Igalaland from the religious perspective. The students in recent times have occupied themselves with a lot of social engagements such as clubbing, pornography, cultic activities, yahooism and many others in order to derive emotional and sexual pleasures. In order to achieve these ends, they engage in cohabiting with their opposite sex for emotional and sexual intimacy, and thereby not having time for their primary assignment as students, which is academic leaning. This paper has a singular aim of bringing to limelight the potential effects of this practice among the male and female students of the higher institutions of learning on academic excellence which is a *sine qua none* for nation building and development. The study finds out through the sociological and phenomenological approaches that a good number of students sent to school by their parents engage in this practice, and if nothing is done urgently, may add up to or compound the existing developmental challenges that

Igalaland is facing; such as failure in examination, unwanted pregnancies, cultic activities, increase in the number of school dropouts, violence, death among others.

Keywords: Cohabitation, Academic performance, Nigeria, Tertiary, Institutions.

Introduction

It is no more an exaggeration that cohabitation among tertiary institutions' students in Nigeria has eroded the level of morality among students. The effect of this practice on academic performance has become more grievous as many have continued to wonder on the decline in academic performance of the tertiary institutions students in current times. The popular and recent sayings among the Nigeria elites that Nigerian graduates in the present time are not employable is a reflection of the obvious fact that there is great decline in academic performance among the tertiary institutions students. Among scholars and researchers, several factors have been adduced as causes of decline in academic performance in the Nigerian Tertiary institutions. These include the neglect of education sector by Nigerian government regimes and corruption that has infiltrated almost all the Nigerian social institutions including educational systems, laxity among parents to carter for their wards in the tertiary institutions, corruption in the school systems among the lecturers and staff of the academic institutions and lack of zeal for learning among students themselves. While all these are contributing factors to decline in academic performance in recent time, cohabitation seems to be more grievous as it is becoming a proper way of life for a good number of students in the institutes of higher learning in Nigeria.

The pathetic state of the practice is that, it is still a strange happening in the ears of many parents who are not aware that wards they sent to school to learn are staying in a lodge with an opposite sex either as a husband or as a wife. The practice of cohabitation is unusual to the African socio-cultural and religious ways of life. And to the Igala people, it is a taboo and an abomination. The parties involved because of its unusual nature, indulges in it secretly as they would not want any of their relations to know. However, the practice in the modern context for the youths seems to be appealing as awards are given to the best cohabiting couples in social parties in the Nigerian institutes of higher learning. A careful look into the learning activities in these higher institutions shows that more harm is caused to learning by existence of this practice as the students have over engaged themselves with more activities and responsibilities beyond or outside learning. The thrust of this paper is to highlight the causes of the practice of cohabitation among the students of tertiary institutions in Igalaland, and to bring out clearly how this becomes a challenge to academic performance, as well as possible ways this practice can be minimized.

The Concept of Cohabitation

Cohabitation in the religious context is a state of living together and having sexual relationship without being married. The term encapsulates the statues and a process that can be seen as alternative type of housing for at least one of the cohabiters (Abdulahi 17). Ekpeyong (153) sees it as a scenario when two people who are romantically involved choose to live together without the formal installment or commitment of marriage. Usually, this kind of union consists typically of emotional and sexual intimacy.

Our focus in this study is campus cohabitation; therefore, this involves a situation where two students, a male and female live together as couple while they are yet to be married. This is said not to be a strange phenomenon. However, the prevalence and popular acceptance of the practice has shifted it from contemporary opinion, to one that is normative experience for young men and young women in present time. Cohabitation among the students of opposite sex is a current phenomenon pervading most, if not all tertiary institutions in Nigeria today as the act has become so rampant to the extent that it has become the usual way of life on the campuses of our higher learning. It is no longer strange nor secret practice as it is now what almost everyone in school knows about, whether involved or not. Almost all the students the researcher asked in Prince Abubakar Audu University in-view of data gathering know about that trend. In some of the social gatherings in schools, award is given to the best cohabiting couples and those involved sees nothing wrong in it, rather are proud of it.

Cohabitation among Tertiary Institutions Students in Igalaland

Cohabitation with an opposite sex partner among Nigerian tertiary institutions may not be a strange or recent practice, as said by some scholars, but the overwhelming acceptance of it in current times has made it a very common practice among the tertiary institutions students. According to Adaaba (12), until recently, cohabitation among students was practiced very secretly, but the huge acceptance given to it in recent times among youths had made the practice becoming a normal practice.³ How and when exactly this practice began in higher institutions is not known; however, it did not just start overnight. According to Unubi (19), the practice of cohabitation did not first start with students in higher institutions, but first existed among the people which later influenced the new generation. In support of Unubi, Adegbe (20) adds that cohabitation among students became a possibility due to the possibility in the increase number of many unmarried couples who have raised homes and their children grew to know that their parents are not formally married. According to this author, the offsprings from these homes may think that cohabitation is part of their culture, and therefore sees nothing wrong with it. Alo and Akinde (10), concord with Adegbe and adds that even though the practice has

some inherent connections, it seems more to be connected with strong urge for sexual gratification among the students among other reasons. Some scholars like Whitehead and Popenoe (26) in addition to sexual gratification purports that sharing of domestic duties like cooking, sweeping and washing of clothes are among other reasons for cohabitation among the students. To this author, male students benefits more from cohabitation than their female counterparts and as such initiates the move first.

Adeoye, Ola and Aliu (12), gave a very critical factor for rise of cohabitation among students of tertiary institutions as they explained that rejection and total abandonment of African values, cultural norms, religion and traditions as the main reasons for this abnormal marriage. To these authors, the parents of these student involved in this practice have alienated their wards long ago from their culture on marriage system which forbids cohabiting with one that you are yet to be married to. This study indicates that those students that are cultured with religious affiliation are less likely to cohabit than those without religious affiliation.

However, it appears that religious inclination is no longer an issue when the present youths want to satisfy their desire to cohabit. It is also not out of place in addition to the above-mentioned factors that rise of the phenomenon of cohabitation stems from misuse, disuses and over use of freedom on the side of the students. This factor explains that lack of adequate monitoring of the students by their parents and guardians is the reasons for misuse of this freedom especially for students that are being free for the first time. In complimenting this position, some scholars have averred that it is not only lack of monitoring from parents, but it includes poverty and inability of the parents to cater for their wards as it should be.

It is no more a news that academic performance among students of tertiary institutions in Nigeria has been on the decline in a very acute proportion. The state of poor performances in academic in recent times poses much threat to economic development, technological advancement and general development in every sector of human endeavor in Nigeria. Failure in academic performance may increase high level of poverty among the populace, particularly the Igala society much known for underdevelopment in Nigeria. In recognition of the importance of education or good academic performance in development of an individual and the society at large, the tertiary institutions are expected to produce viable graduates who should be able to manage sensitive positions to foster development in the country. In view of this expectation, Akeji (19) maintains that it is a general consensus that meaningful development cannot be recorded except there is proper development of human resources, which can only be achieved through education. Therefore, formal education is regarded as the main tool for socio-economic development and social mobilization in any society. Also, any nation hoping to have bright future needs to emphasize education and merit performance of it (Pat-Mbano 12).

It is very alarming in recent times that academic performance of students among the tertiary institutions in Igalaland has become lamentable. In the process of investigation and data collection for this research, the researcher was able to meet with some students of the main three tertiary institutions to ask questions on the subject matter. It is quite surprising that this phenomenon has eaten deep into the fabrics of the academic system, as almost all the students across these schools are aware of this phenomenon. The level at which they tolerate the phenomenon instead of having a sober reflection was very strange to the researcher. At Prince Abubakar Audu University, ten students: six females and four males were interviewed. Out the six females who agreed that such practice is on increase on the campus, only one accepted to have been involved. And among the four male students, two agreed to have been involved in the practice of cohabitation, while the remaining two are aware of the existence of the practice but claimed not to have practiced it.

Another tertiary institution visited was the Kogi State College of Education Ankpa. In the same vein, about ten students were interviewed on the subject of cohabitation. Out of the six females interviewed, only two agreed to have cohabited with their male counterparts says temporarily. However, the other two do not claim to be novices about cohabitation. Among the males interviewed, only one agreed to have been involved. The third among the schools visited is the Federal Polytechnic Idah, where about more than ten students were interviewed. Out of the six females interviewed, only one agreed to have cohabited and the remaining five claimed to know such thing existed. Of the four males, all claimed to have been involved in cohabitation. Among the reasons for cohabitation given included misuse of freedom from the control of their parents, socialization and civilization which has become a new trend, uncontrollable sexual desires among the youths of this generation and the need for compliments in engagement of domestic work, economic and poverty state of the nation and Igalaland in particular etc. The fact that all the students interviewed failed to disclose their full identify except their first name, Departments and Levels in their schools shows the secretive nature of the practice of cohabitation among the students. To the question as to whether cohabitation has some adverse effect on academic performance among these campuses, the response of the interviewed students was yes. Let's take a look at how cohabitation affects academic performance.

Effects of Cohabitation on Academic Performance of Tertiary institutions students in Igalaland

From the foregoing, it is crystal clear that the practice of cohabitation has become common among the tertiary institution students in a very well-cultured society like Igalaland. It is very true also from every indication, that the practice has much adverse effect on the lives of the people of Igala society which includes the academic performance of the tertiary institutions students. Sometimes students

involve in cohabitation ignorantly because they do not understand the repercussion of cohabitating. Thousands of students of both males and females still practice cohabitation and this has continued to mar their studies. From the study so far, many students in their studies graduate with lower grades or ordinary pass, while others have been expelled from schools for examination malpractice or inability to pass a good number of courses. The pathetic state of it is when some who are gifted cohabiters managed to scale through their academic programme without any serious impact on their learning: This has helped to produce half – baked graduates who may not be able to cope with intellectual demands of the fast developing society as obtainable in current times. The Following are various ways the students involved in cohabitations are affected by it:

- i. **Lack of concentration:** - Once a student begins to cohabit, it becomes very practical that he/she loses his or her concentration on academics. This is because cohabitation as a practice must be given attention and then pursuit of academic might not be primary focus on the students cohabiting. Adejoh (20), in his study on the effects of the cohabitation among Igala youths confirmed that the lack or loss of concentration is caused by the loss of the individual's freedom or liberty to live his or her life. This he said, affects the female students mostly as she loses right to say no on issues which ordinarily she would have refused. One of the students interviewed at PAAU (Inikpi hostel) gives examples on this note as she says if one's partner is ill, as female cohabiter, it becomes difficult for one to attend lectures nor be able to read because she needs to go round to ensure that her boyfriend becomes healthy. Even if she misses test, attendance and other continuous assessment activities, it worth it. This and more others are ways that the cohabiting students fall short of the learning standards of the tertiary institutions. (Aduku, oral interview)
- ii. **Engagement in Anti – Social Behaviour:** The students cohabiting are not only prone to distractions over their academic activities, but are also open to anti-social behavior. They engaged in armed robbery activities and cultism, clubbing, yahooism, and many other malevolent activities (Uchendu 21). The main three tertiary institutions of learning in Igalaland have a good number of records of these activities engaged by students. A careful observation on reported cases in the various security units of these institutions proved this very clearly. From the researcher's investigation, it is hard for students who engage in cohabitation to be without involvement in any of these anti-social behaviour. Unfortunately, their engagement in these negative vices make them not to have time for their primary assignment in School, and as such, there is much decline in their academic performances.

- iii. **Spread of Diseases and Unwanted pregnancy:** The students involved in cohabitation sees themselves as husband and wife and so, could some time have unprotected sexual intercourse. This has led to the spread of diseases such as HIV/AIDs, syphilis, Hepatitis B and many other sexually transmitted diseases. As a result, these students may not be able to concentration on their academics. The female folks are at more disadvantaged position according to Oyewole (21), because they are not only open up to these diseases but could have unwanted pregnancy. Undoubtedly, unwanted pregnancy that stands to be a shameful thing in the past in Igalaland and among Igala people has become very rampant and shameless. It does not require any investigation anymore to know how many ladies get pregnant in a session or semester while yet to be married (Ameh 18). The unwanted pregnancy and all its attendant consequences either lowered the academic participation of the student or have capacity to worsen the situation to the extent that the student can be withdrawn from the school for extreme poor performance. All these can be initiated by the practice of cohabitation.

Igalaland and Poor Academic Performance

The word “Igala” refers to the people and language of one of the largest ethnic groups in the former Kabba province of northern Nigeria. The vast land occupied by Igala people is located at the eastern flank of what is known as the confluence of rivers Niger and Benue (Igono 20). Until 1991, the people were under Benue State, but now with the creation of Kogi State in the said year, Igala people fell to the newly created state as the largest and dominating ethnic group in the state. In the present time, the people occupied nine out of the twenty one Local Government areas in the state. The formal education system was the greatest impact and achievement of the early Christian missionaries in Igalaland which was admired, cherished and celebrated among the people for its good, sound and adequate moral building and character molding of the society. It is regrettable that learning and outstanding academic outputs the Igala Nation was known for has been recently bastardized on the account of moral laxity of which the practice of cohabitation can be part of (Ademu 21). While cohabitation may not be the remote and main reason for decline in academic performance, it contributes substantially in recent time.

It is true that there is failure of academic performance all over Nigeria which have been identified and queried by a good number of scholarly considerations (Aremu 23), but the spate at which it is falling among the observed tertiary institutions in very alarming. Failure in learning is not only frustrating the students and their parents, but its effects are equally crucial on the society in terms of lack of manpower in all fields of human endeavour. Academic performance refers to the degree of a student’s accomplishment, his or her task and studies. The most-well

known indicator of measuring academic performance is grades which reflects the students "Score" for their subjects and overall tenure. Considering the performance of the examined results across the higher institutions in the cause of this research, one could notice that a good number of students fall to the last class of grading as either pass, third class and in some cases certificate of attendance. Even though some have generally dismissed the use of academic score grading system as impotent tool for assessment of academic performance due to much corruption and compromise that possibly exist in the higher institutions of learning among students, lecturers and school administrators.

There is no gain saying that the scoring system may have been totally bastardized. The position of the researcher here is that since there is no alternative mode of assessing academic performance; what we may say is that the scoring and grading system is not enough. It is now necessary to judge students' performance from the point of view of their social life versus academic life, their reading habit, lack of specific goal and study plan, procrastination and lukewarm attitude towards learning. All these are the indices the researcher has used to aver that there is great decline in academic performance, which he felt one of the recent and contemporary factor could be the practice of cohabitation.

The Religious Perspective

The Igala people practice the three main religions in Nigeria: Christianity, Islam and African Traditional Religion. None of these religions permits the practice of cohabitation, rather the practice is condemnable by all and sundry. The three religions support consummation of marriage rites before parties can live together (Ladan, Ameh, & Eleojo in oral interview). According to Ayodeji (27), we don't need to do much of exegetical and hermeneutical discourses in order to know how wrong cohabitation is among Christians and Muslims. The author adds that among the African Traditional religious adherents, it is also a taboo to co-live with an opposite sex why yet to be married. It is surprising then that a good number of the students cohabiting are either for any of these three main religions. It shows that the hold of religion on morality is now becoming questionable, more so that some of the cohabiters are functioning very well in religious gatherings and fellowships without any indication that they are in such practice. It is however quite understandable that while cohabitation is a condemnable practice everywhere in these religions, attention is yet to be given to how evil it is among students in recent times.

Recommendations

In view of the foregoing discourse on the challenge of cohabitation among the tertiary institutions in Igalaland and its effects on Academic performance which has

resulted in the decline of the later, the following recommendations are considered necessary:

- i. The students are advised to deviate from this practice as involvement in it has the capacity to mar their destiny. The researcher recommends to students to be discipline and be decisive in their choice of action. They should know also that cohabitation is immoral and with damming consequences.
- ii. The study recommends to the parents to be paying unscheduled visits to their wards in their lodges. Apart from this, they should also keep on reminding their wards on the sacredness of Igala culture in relation to this practice.
- iii. The school authorities should build more hostel accommodation to accommodate a large percentage of their students as this will bring more, if not the majority under the control of the school authority (Agboola 22). In addition to this, the schools should create awareness on the consequences of cohabitation among the students and punitive measures to be meted out to students who indulge in it.
- iv. The religious institutions in Igalaland and those on the school campuses should put more efforts to emphasize in their teachings on consequences of cohabitation as well as what the sacred books have said regarding this phenomenon. This will hopefully rebirth religious consciousness that may be a panacea to this uncultured practice.
- v. The Government should promulgate law and policies that will include cohabitation among students as unlawful. They should also assist the school authorities with fund that will avail them more accommodation facilities for students.

Conclusion

From the foregoing, it is obvious that there is much decline in academic performance among the students of Tertiary institutions in Nigeria generally and Igalaland in particular. The study has clarified that one of the recent factors for poor performance in students' academics among many others is the practice of cohabitation among the opposite sex. The study has recognized this practice from the religious perspective as evil that should be avoided. Various reasons leading to this practice were identified and its consequences outlined. Before arriving at this point, efforts have been made in this study to clarify on the concept of cohabitation from the religious perspective which simply means a state of living together and having sexual relationship without being married. It encapsulates the statues and a process that can be seen as alternative type of marriage or housing. The study went further to look into how this practice is being perpetrated among the tertiary institutions in Igalaland, the challenges of the practice and its effects on the students and the society at large.

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Appendix

List of Interviewees

S/N	Sex	Occupation	Name	Place	Positions	Date	Age
1	Male	Civil servant	Ameh Abdul	Ajiyolo-Ojaji	Secondary School Teacher	August 14 th , 2025	54
2	Male	Civil Servant	Suleman Ladan	Anyigba	Lecturer at PAAU	September 15 th , 2025	55
3	Female	Civil Servant	Edibo Elejojo	Anyigba	Lecturer At PAAU	October 15 th , 2025	56
4	Male	Civil Servant	Aduku Omale	Ankpa	A Land Lord/ Estate manager	October 10 th 2024	70
5	Male	Civil Servant	Ichado Abraham	Idah	Lecturer/ Land Lord	11 th Oct, 2024	60